

REMEDIAL ACTIVITIES FOR NON-STEM SCIENCE MAJOR STUDENTS OF BATANGAS STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the extent of manifestation of science competencies of first year BSEd Sciences major students of College of Teacher Education, who are non-STEM graduates, in biology, chemistry and physics, with the end view of proposing remedial activities. It also assessed practices applied in teaching and learning on these science courses. Further, challenges encountered by the students in learning were also identified. The study used descriptive research design using a questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. Respondents of the study were students of Batangas State University-Pablo Borbon, Batangas State University-Malvar, and Batangas State University-Nasugbu (ARASOF). Statistical tools used were composite and weighted mean. The results revealed that first year BSEd Sciences program students who are non-STEM graduates' manifest slight competence in Biology and Physics while moderate competence in Chemistry. In terms of teaching and learning practices, students strongly agree that watching educational videos, relating learning to daily lives and watching the teacher demonstrate an experiment or investigation were commonly applied while conducting experiments and investigations, designing an experiment or investigation and reading articles and describing what they have read were the least used. Respondents agreed that they often encounter challenges in solving scientific problems in chemistry and physics, insufficient prior knowledge from SHS and memorization of scientific terms and information. Failure to recognize interconnectedness of science lessons, huge number of students in a class and competence of teacher were sometimes encountered. Based on the findings, the researchers came up with a compilation of remedial activities in which selected topics in SHS curriculum guide were considered.

Keywords: Competencies, Senior High School, Strand, Non-STEM, Remedial Activities, Philippines